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11. Uluslararası Akademik Araştırmalar Kongresi (ICAR)

National Security Risk of Military Privatization with PMC: The Wagner Case

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Abstract

Private Military Companies (PMCs) are the privatization of military services. Historically, the problems of mercenarism are generally the same as they are today, starting with the rights that nations surrender with their own hands and ending with the consequences of privatized mercenaries creating disorder. There are many risks and dangers that come with and will come with mercenary organizations operating internationally or nationally. The Wagner Group emerged during the conflict in Crimea and has been operating worldwide ever since, with Russia using PMC services more actively as a result of the Gerasimov Doctrine in 2014. Given the recent crisis between the Wagner Group and the Russian government, it is doubtful that mercenary or specialized military structures pose a risk to national security. Within the framework of the concept of security of nations, it is necessary to identify the threats and risks of specialized mercenary formations to the security of states, as well as what measures should be taken, using the example of the Wagner Group.

Keywords: National Security, PMC, Private Military Company, Wagner Group

Özet

Özel Askeri Şirketler (Private Military Companies- PMC'ler) askeri hizmetlerin özelleştirilmesidir. Tarihi olarak paralı askerlikte genel itibariyle problemler günümüzle aynıdır, bu problemler ulusların kendi elleriyle teslim ettikleri haklarla başlar ve özelleşmiş yani paralı askerlerin başıbozukluk yaratması sonuçlarına ulaşmasıyla son bulur. Uluslararası veya ulusal faaliyet gösteren paralı asker yapılarının getirmiş olduğu ve getireceği birçok risk ve tehlike de söz konusudur. Bu noktada Rusya'nın 2014'teki Gerasimov Doktrini sonucunda PMC hizmetlerini daha aktif bir şekilde kullanmasıyla Wagner Grubu, Kırım'daki ihtilaf sırasında ortaya çıkmış ve o zamandan beri dünya çapında faaliyet göstermektedir. Wagner Grubu ve Rus hükümeti arasında çıkan son kriz göz önüne alındığında paralı askerlik ya da özelleşmiş askeri yapıların ulusal güvenlik için bir risk teşkil ettiği şüphe uyandırmıştır. Ulusların güvenlik kavramı çerçevesinde, Wagner Grubu örneğiyle uzmanlaşmış paralı asker oluşumlarının devletlerin güvenliğine yönelik tehdit ve risklerinin yanı sıra ne tür önlemler alınması gerektiğini tespit etmek gerekmektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Ulusal Güvenlik, PMC, Özel Askeri Şirket, Wagner Group

INTRODUCTION

Private Military Companies (PMCs) are the privatization of military services. While the origins of privatization date back to antiquity, modern military services became active in the late 20th century. In the 1990s, as the Cold War waned, private military organizations increased and nation states resorted to limiting official military services. Privatized military institutions provide security or protection services through consultancy and training. In order to strengthen military forces, states support modern private military structures.

Machiavelli refers to mercenarism as "useless and dangerous". This is because historical analysis has shown that privatized military structures are characterized by the commercialization of their moral concepts and the use of semi-official state power to engage in unprincipled behavior. For these reasons, Machiavelli expressed a disdainful view of Private Military and Security Companies (PMSC), i.e. mercenaries. Military history shows that even great empires have hired, trained and, when necessary, used mercenaries in a manner similar to irregular warfare. The aim of states here is to operate in the most effective way with the customized military systems in addition to the regular designs of their armed forces (Casiraghi, 2022).

Of course, there is no single reason for nations to opt for military privatization. Some states use privatized mercenary formations to provide technology and human resources, including various specialties, as evidenced by the decisions of their national security councils and activities. In this way, the state achieves a dual function by preventing its military from over-exerting itself and by instilling the idea of performing a noble mission through the participation of mercenaries from the civilian population with different competencies. With this type of method, a public and diplomatic secret power is created to avoid danger with both sources of military structures. In order to put this system into practice, it is publicized as a local and society-wide idea, which can be considered as an invitation to military privatization in the whole society, thus providing an environment of trust and preventing possible risks (Cusumano, & Kinsey, 2022).

For centuries, state leaders have aimed to reduce costs while trying to increase the efficiency of military forces. Political and diplomatic objectives are another factor in increasing efficiency (Casiraghi, 2022). At this point, it should be noted that the aim of the research is to reveal what kind of measures should be taken by addressing the threats and risks of specialized and mercenary formations to the security of nations.

Another aspect that needs to be assessed is that under Vladimir Putin's leadership, Russia's enhanced military power acts as a national threat in the international system. Although PMCs are seen as a balancing force or quasi-state force, the rise of semi-official PMCs has put Russia and other countries at significant risk to their internal security. It should be noted that private military structures are composed of former Russian state soldiers, veterans and other security forces, including the Wagner Group. This is another reason that underpins the quasi-state power conception of security. At this point, other PMCs in the defense of national order, such as Cossack PMC soldiers and Wagner-affiliated PMC soldiers, may pose an additional danger in the event that they are not willing to obey the law. Mercenary armed groups first appeared in Russia in the early 1990s as the Soviet Union was disintegrating. Under the leadership of Boris Yeltsin, the concept of "volunteer detachments" emerged. Unofficial (volunteer

detachments) specialized military structures carried out security operations in the Eurasian space and for the interests of the former Yugoslavia. While most of the volunteers were identified as Cossacks, they were contracted locally by Soviet Russia with quasi-state power to protect and secure the Russian borders and to pacify threats posed by minorities (Marten, 2019). As in the case of the Wagner group, a military and civilian model was developed with patrimonial ties within law enforcement and the military, beyond the state in general. For this reason, the more important situation is that mercenaries who act as mavericks by underestimating the orders of their governments will constitute another national and international problem and are a security issue that nations need to address carefully (Cusumano, & Kinsey, 2022).

Attention should be paid to the danger that privatized mercenary systems may create national security problems in the national sense and what measures should be taken against such problems. Similarly, a security approach needs to be created based on the example of the Wagner Group, which has been going on since antiquity and continues today with the modernized concept of privatization and has created a national problem in Russia. Some mercenary formations like Wagner, which are perceived as semi-professional by definition, do not actually carry innocence because they are trained by people who are specialized and have received various military training. Another important situation is that they can pose an international national security problem with their potential to act in a way that does not take orders from the official military members in the region when they are deployed in any operational activity or battlefield (Casiraghi, 2022). Our aim in this study is to provide policy makers and states with the perspective of various solutions and measures to be taken in this regard within the framework of security sciences, national and international crime prevention and national defense.

METHOD

Our research aims to identify the reasons why national security and military privatization risk becoming a threat to nations and what measures various nations and unions can take. Our methodology is based on literature studies and cases conducted on behalf of the Wagner Group. Recommendations from these literature studies were taken into account, and different cases were evaluated where applicable. Inferences were drawn by comparing similar studies. We prioritized countries with large military power. The reason for this is to reach more accurate and efficient overall analysis results. In conclusion, the importance of international cooperation and dialogue to protect national security was emphasized. International cooperation and dialogue can help build a common understanding of military specialization and contribute to the international community developing a common strategy and agreement on this issue.

RESULTS

Anthony Mockler's 'History of Mercenaries', which is the most referenced work on the concept of mercenaries in the history of warfare, is important in the historiography of war and warfare. It has been determined that mercenaries have been used in various warfare methods throughout the ages (Riemann, 2022). Here Riemann states that mercenarism cannot be an ahistorical structure and that it existed before the modern period. In connection with the data obtained from the past to the present, it is noteworthy that labeling these people with the concepts of mercenary and specialized army creates political and social motivation, that is, the affirmation that they have adopted the principle to serve the

institution, organization or public with this labeling. It should not be forgotten that the fact that mercenarism has been or will be instrumentalized and influenced by nation states and their advocates constitutes a critical fine line. Because if a socio-political motivation with the label of a privatized army turns into the idea of fighting not for their nation but purely for money, it causes PMCs to leave the national consciousness and enter psychological warfare, demotivating them and posing a threat to the nation itself (Cusumano, & Kinsey, 2022).

Recently, there have been problems with the Wagner Group with central Russia (Clarke, 2023). However, while PMC structures are not included in current Russian military theories, the Wagner Group and other PMSCs cannot be denied by the Kremlin as a specialized military phenomenon whose existence is governed solely by commercial laws, and their activities continue. In some Russian works on future warfare, PMSCs are understood as one of the diplomatic choices for Russian security understanding and policy, as it is based on the Western phenomenon. There are discussions among Russian authorities to increase and develop the Russian PMSC industry. There are a few strong proposals for PMCs, mainly based on the reasons for choosing them: profit, i.e. costs, military emulation or simulation, and avoidance of human casualties (Bukkvoll, & Ostensen, 2020).

Another reason why mercenarism has been preferred throughout history is cost, as hiring forces is preferred to reduce costs. In a regular army, on the other hand, it is costly to continuously source resources. Mercenaries can pose a national security threat, like the Wagner Group, if their costs are not met or if (political) promises are not fulfilled (McFate, 2019).

When historical analysis is analyzed, another reason for choosing private military armed structures is their covert potential. They have a significant impact in preventing espionage problems and engaging in active counter-espionage activities, national and international. It is important to note that PMCs do not perform these activities only for the state and politicians, their approach is commercial. On this basis, it is also possible for them to create a security vulnerability within the nation itself. It is important that PMC members have the foresight and training to recognize whether their activities are spying or providing intelligence (Casiraghi, 2022).

For example, Wagner or other specialized military companies providing mercenary services in Russia have actually become legalized when they acquired commercial qualifications. There is no formalized legal regulation for PMCs in Russia and the Russian Criminal Code prohibits mercenary services from participating in any war. This makes PMCs in Russia attractive for covertly serving Russian foreign policy in operational activities. Countries that have not legalized these structures, such as Russia, are likely to have their national problems exposed in disputes with these military privatizations (Reynolds, 2019). Therefore, PMCs that are not subject to national laws need to be brought under the provisions of international law. In the 1989 United Nations (UN) Convention and earlier discussions on PMSCs, whose legal existence was questioned, mercenarism was defined in Article 47 of the 1977 Additional Protocol to the Geneva Convention (Bures, & Cusumano, 2021).

PMSCs are primarily preferred by the Chinese state and local service providers because of the availability of specialized managers and specialists with higher security. In addition, they provide mercenary military services using high and advanced technologies. Their ability to operate overseas is directly proportional to the technology used (Yuan, 2022). In addition, it is worth noting that the Wagner

Group or Russian PMCs are mostly composed of people with experienced military skills and expertise. For example, PMCs, which include veterans and retirees who know how to use advanced military systems and have been involved in counter-terrorism activities, know the military structure of their respective nations well, which could pose a national security problem one day, as in the case of Wagner (Bukkvoll, & Østensen, 2020).

In September 2018, Putin further complicated the situation by issuing a decree on "Cooperation with non-employees of foreign intelligence of the Russian Federation", according to which the activities of the Wagner Group and other PMCs will be considered a state secret. But it is impossible to see how mercenarism, which is already illegal, can be subject to decrees. Even Vladimir Neelov, a defense analyst, who had suggested this, was arrested for treason. In any country, such problems will pose a national security threat to the states themselves, as long as they have no legal basis. In other ways, major international states have already regulated PMCs through legislation. The United States, China, France and the United Kingdom, as well as other permanent members of the United Nations Security Council (UNSC), have taken joint legal decisions by signing the 2008 International Committee of the Red Cross Montreux Document (Marten, 2019).

Securing these entities by law is important for national security but will not entirely eliminate the risks associated with PMCs. For example, as in African regions, the Federal Government of Nigeria and the minority and separatist mercenaries in Biafra, the National Union for Total Independence (UNITA) and the National Front for Total Independence (FNLA) used PMC mercenaries for the liberation of Angola, but of course this was not the final solution (Okosa, 2023). However, it should not be forgotten that during the war between Russia and Ukraine, the Wagner Group in Ukraine did not receive sufficient support from the Russian authorities, which is thought to be a result of old military-political problems, not logistical problems. It is possible to see similar situations in national security threats that may arise in other countries (McFate, 2019).

By Executive Order 13581, established in 2011 to crack down on "transnational criminal organizations" in the US, the Wagner Group was declared a transnational criminal organization as a structure that poses "an unusual and extraordinary threat to the national security of the United States". In Russia, despite the Wagner Group's defiance, it is not considered a criminal organization. This is because another danger Russia poses with PMCs is the use of mercenaries to protect energy resources such as Gazprom. It is obvious that this situation poses a series of risks to national security, especially the economy (Clarke, 2023).

PMSCs in South Africa have a strict prohibitive legal basis. This advanced regulation is a decision taken by the South African government for the security stability of the continent and the region (Kimble, & Bosch, 2022). Similar to the example of the Wagner Group, which operated regionally and continentally, the US PMC mercenaries Blackwater, which has a negative reputation in the world, had problems with national and international organizations and created national security concerns in the US (Marten, 2019). Another national risk of specialized military structures is that they may find themselves capable of attacking and defending cities and towns with regional analogies like Kabul and Baghdad in the case of Mogadishu (Norman, 2023). PMCs operating in different countries, such as the Wagner Group, therefore pose a national danger. The Wagner Group has worked in large areas such as Syria, Sudan,

Libya, Central African Republic (CAR), Venezuela, Burkina Faso, Mozambique, Madagascar, Algeria, Mali, Eritrea, Cameroon (Clarke, 2023). Often, policymakers of countries with such internal unrest and national problems use mercenary structures, and it is possible to identify that politicians are even shareholders of PMCs. For example, Somalia's Minister of Internal Security was a shareholder of an international mercenary company, another problem that puts public and state security in a critical predicament (Kimble, & Bosch, 2022).

Like Russia's PMCs, countries with great global power, like Russia's PMCs, have increasingly realized that their use of low-cost military services in response to external threats and border threats can come at a heavy cost. As an additional problem, they are increasingly aware of the erosion of their political power (Cusumano, & Kinsey, 2022). Similarly, specialized military security formations concentrated in the Green Zone in Mogadishu have created a security risk by creating a climate of political violence against the state and public security, even as they have attempted to provide security in Somalia (Norman, 2023).

In 2017, both the US PMCs and Special Operations Forces and Russia's activities with the Wagner Group in Syria were favored for deniability reasons, but their emergence threatened their respective countries with political and policy crises (Cusumano, & Kinsey, 2022).

In a different example, in response to the Boko Haram problem in Northwest and Northeast Nigeria, they opted for international PMCs for unregulated bandits and insurgents (Yusuf, & Zakari, 2023). Mercenaries have been active against Boko Haram in different forces and have made deals with Nigeria's military, but the deals have been partially effective (Singh, & Singh, 2022). However, in situations that cause civil unrest, such as Boko Haram, nations are often misled by the dual nature of some mercenary structures. For this reason, it is determined that the effective use of PMCs for national security is not appropriate (Yusuf, & Zakari, 2023).

Mercenaries, or PMCs, also offer cyber mercenary services according to the services requested by their governments and private institutions or organizations (da Cruz, & Pedron, 2020). As in the case of the Wagner Group, it is possible for mercenary structures formed by former military personnel and security experts to use technologies for advanced operational activities (Cusumano, & Kinsey, 2022). Chinese PMCs, for example, utilize big data mines, artificial intelligence systems, internet-based networks, robotics, and cyber networks in their use of high technologies. PMCs are nationally and internationally preferred because they can include mercenaries who use high and advanced technologies and are well versed in specialized forms of cyber attack and defense (Yuan, 2022).

Of course, the cyber mercenary system has various risks. Because these data, which contain the most confidential matters in providing national intelligence, pose a high risk of being used as a threat against state leaders (da Cruz, & Pedron, 2020). One of the cyber risks of the Wagner group, defamation propaganda through the Internet Research Agency, is a bad example of cyber mercenary activity. Cyber mercenary or PMC structures are capable of creating many national dangers such as greater economic, political, civil unrest, information leakage, etc. with the logic of cyber army in every country (Charamba, & Megret, 2023).

It is thought that some problems can be avoided by regulating the PMC industry. First of all, it should be emphasized that each country should do its own legal work for this situation. Providing ISO 28007-1:2015 or International Code of Conduct (ICOC) and ISO 18788:2015- Management System for Private Security Operations standards to provide standards for international mercenary or PMCs is important to prevent some national problems (Kimble, & Bosch, 2022).

Some analysts in China have discussed hazard prevention in three stages. At the national level, first, government and policymakers need to conduct risk assessments. Second, it is essential to measure the capabilities of PMCs. To reduce national risks and prevent loss of life and property, it is necessary to know the capabilities of specialized security services (Yuan, 2022). It is observed that the Wagner Group, for example, cannot be penalized for its activities under the name of mercenary and specialized security services that are not eligible for full legal penalties internationally or nationally, but only sanctions can be imposed (Charamba, & Megret, 2023).

As a contrast, although states have used PMC mercenaries against PMC mercenaries in domestic political problems, tough measures to prevent PMCs from getting involved in domestic problems can still be implemented through decisions taken by diplomats (Neethling, 2023). Another example is the use of mercenaries in Africa, where official forces have tried to prevent casualties. Here, PMCs, which are a risk for the state itself, will be prevented by public law enforcement when they pose a threat to any state. In such a situation, it is possible for official forces to be killed by PMCs without rules (Singh, & Singh, 2022).

The Wagner Group in Russia and other PMCs should not be left as an open-ended structure in countries. The dichotomy should be eliminated by defining the position of mercenaries within policy makers and existing regimes, and a diplomatic belt should be created between PMC mercenary security military structures and the state regime (Østensen, & Bukkvoll, 2022).

The training of the Wagner Group in the GRU (Main Intelligence Directorate) facility with a sense of duty in foreign operations, for example in Nigeria and similar places, and the provision of leadership-based information and equipping them, and the awarding of state medals of courage and honor, is an important activity in ensuring national security. The best example of this situation is the Wagner organization in 2023, which rebelled against the Russian authorities, but psychologically and due to their power from the past, it caused them to gain control over the country's administration (Marten, 2019).

In order to prevent private military companies from becoming a national problem, broad framework regulations need to be put in place and these need to be mutually agreed upon. However, drafting laws and regulations does not create deterrent factors. Enacted provisions are essential (Casiraghi, & Cusumano, 2023). As a pioneer, the outlines of a definitive and descriptive crime prevention document for national and public security against hazardous and risky environments to be realized by PMCs were drawn by the recommendations of the United Kingdom (Beyani, & Lilly, 2001). The people of the countries should be informed about the negative situations that specialized mercenary formations can create in the country through media power and awareness-raising methods as well as education. Young members who are included in PMC memberships in the future with ideological approaches will stop

being a threat and will not pose a national risk if their attitudes are close to national spiritual views in the face of internal threat situations (Nabiev, 2021).

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

In the history of warfare, the concept of mercenarism has been important from the past (Riemann, 2022). Although they operate to serve states, there is always a critical fine line. This is because all PMCs are engaged in commercial activities, and if they are not compensated, they pose a national risk (Cusumano, & Kinsey, 2022).

When we look at security research, the recent problems with the Wagner Group and central Russia have been mainly due to costs, logistical problems, and covert interference in politics (Clarke, 2023). The point of discussion here is the contrast between the national security problem between the Wagner Group and Russia, as well as the preference for PMCs, despite the fact that mercenaries have been subjected to the unrest caused by mercenaries by states throughout history for certain reasons (Bukkvoll, & Østensen, 2020).

In another case, PMCs working nationally and internationally engage in intelligence activities. Here, they do not act with national considerations because their approach is commercial. In this case, the problem of being able to spy where they should be providing intelligence may arise (Casiraghi, M. C. (2022). The same, of course, applies to cyber mercenary services, especially when national secrets are leaked to the public, posing a problem for internal security (da Cruz, & Pedron, 2020). As an example, the Wagner Group's cyber activity against the state, discussed in the findings, is the defamation propaganda with the Internet Research Agency. Therefore, the concept of an official cyber army should be built into national security programs and countermeasures should be taken, especially against PMCs (Charamba, & Megret, 2023).

PMCs, made up of former law enforcement officers of countries, know how the country's official system dynamics move (Bukkvoll, & Østensen, 2020). For example, in 2018, a decision was taken to ban consultations with Wagner and PMCs that "cooperate with those who do not work with foreign intelligence of the Russian Federation". The situation here is that PMCs do not have a certain status in the law, except commercially. As a precautionary measure, internationally, the US, China, France and the UK, as well as other permanent members of the United Nations Security Council (UNSC), signed the 2008 International Committee of the Red Cross Montreux Document, but its binding and enforceability is questionable (Marten, 2019). Politicians have been found to be shareholders of PMCs, as in the case of the Wagner Group, which operates across national borders and internationally. In such a situation, national security is in serious danger (Kimble, & Bosch, 2022).

Considering the recent crisis between Wagner and the Russian government, the most fundamental measure that each country should take in order to ensure national security, which we have examined through the example of mercenarism and the Wagner Group, is the establishment of legal grounds. Because inductively, each of the laws of the countries will form a chain model for the implementation of international laws and provisions. In the next stage, private military companies or mercenaries should be trained for the control of private military companies or mercenaries nationally, subjected to a certain state network, and the information of their inventories in terms of vehicles and equipment should be

provided for internal audit and control by public institutions, internal security or law enforcement agencies. In addition, PMC licensing, setting ethical rules and standards, cooperation and information sharing with state institutions for control, preparation of national security plans for PMCs, and periodic detailed review and reporting of their activities are extremely necessary.

REFERENCE

Casiraghi, M. C. (2022). ‘Useless and dangerous’? Mercenaries in fourteenth century wars. *Small Wars & Insurgencies*, 33(1-2), 71-91. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09592318.2021.1956109>

Cusumano, E., & Kinsey, C. (2022). Concluding comments. *Small Wars & Insurgencies*, 33(1-2), 294-312. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09592318.2022.2021487>

Marten, K. (2019). Russia’s use of semi-state security forces: the case of the Wagner Group. *Post-Soviet Affairs*, 35(3), 181-204. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1060586X.2019.1591142>

Cusumano, E., & Kinsey, C. (2022). Advancing private security studies: introduction to the special issue. *Small Wars & Insurgencies*, 33(1-2), 1-21. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09592318.2022.2021486>

Riemann, M. (2022). Mercenaries in/and history: the problem of ahistoricism and contextualism in mercenary scholarship. *Small Wars & Insurgencies*, 33(1-2), 22-47. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23296151.2020.1740528>

Bukkvoll, T., & Østensen, Å. G. (2020). The emergence of Russian private military companies: a new tool of clandestine warfare. *Special Operations Journal*, 6(1), 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23296151.2020.1740528>

McFate, S. (2019). Mercenaries and war: understanding private armies today. <https://ndupress.ndu.edu/Media/News/Article/2031922/mercenaries-and-war-understanding-private-armies-today/>

Reynolds, N. (2019). Putin's Not-so-secret Mercenaries: Patronage, Geopolitics, and the Wagner Group (Vol. 8). Washington, DC: Carnegie Endowment for International Peace. [extension://bfdogplmndidlpjhojckpakkdjkkil/pdf/viewer.html?file=https%3A%2F%2Fcarnegeiendowment.org%2Ffiles%2FGlobalRussia_NateReynolds_Vagner.pdf](https://www.carnegieendowment.org/files/GlobalRussia_NateReynolds_Vagner.pdf)

Bures, O., & Cusumano, E. (2021). The anti-mercenary norm and united nations’ use of private military and security companies: from norm entrepreneurship to organized hypocrisy. *International peacekeeping*, 28(4), 579-605. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13533312.2020.1869542>

Yuan, J. (2022). China’s private security companies and the protection of Chinese economic interests abroad. *Small Wars & Insurgencies*, 33(1-2), 173-195. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09592318.2021.1940646>

- Okosa, C. B. (2023). Legality Of Use Of Mercenaries In Nigeria’s Counter -Terrorism Protocol. *Unizik Law Journal*, 19(2). <https://www.journals.ezenwaohaetorc.org/index.php/ULJ/article/view/2291/2332>
- Clarke, C., (2023). What Happens Next with the Wagner Group?. United States of America. Retrieved from: Jul 2023. CID: 20.500.12592/rsnh2q. <https://policycommons.net/artifacts/3834891/what-happens-next-with-the-wagner-group/4640765/>
- Kimble, M., & Bosch, S. (2022). Private military and security companies: South Africa’s neglected resource. *African Security Review*, 31(3), 317-331. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10246029.2022.2104653>
- Norman, J. (2023). Porous bunker: Private security contractors and the plasticity of Mogadishu’s international ‘green zone.’ *Security Dialogue*, 54(3), 290–309. <https://doi.org/10.1177/09670106231158890>
- Yusuf, M. A., & Zakari, L. (2023). Non-Formal Education Options For Addressing Security Challenges In North-East And North-West Nigeria. *IJIET (International Journal of Indonesian Education and Teaching)*, 7(1), 121-135. <https://doi.org/10.24071/ijiet.v7i1.4642>
- Singh, A., & Singh, A. (2022). Mercenaries in Africa: legality and geopolitics. *African Journal of Economic and Sustainable Development*, 9(1), 23-36. <https://doi.org/10.1504/AJESD.2022.125006>
- da Cruz, J. D. A., & Pedron, S. (2020). Cyber Mercenaries: A New Threat to National Security. *International Social Science Review*, 96(2), 1b-1b. <https://digitalcommons.northgeorgia.edu/issr/vol96/iss2/3>
- Charamba, K., & Megret, F. (2023). Wagner, PMSCs, and the Limits of Transnational Governance. <https://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4418518>
- Neethling, T. (2023). Russian Para-Military Operations in Africa: The Wagner Group as a De Facto Foreign Policy Instrument. *Scientia Militaria: South African Journal of Military Studies*, 51(1), 1-23. <https://doi.org/10.5787/51-1-1403>
- Østensen, Å. G., & Bukkvoll, T. (2022). Private military companies—Russian great power politics on the cheap?. *Small Wars & Insurgencies*, 33(1-2), 130-151. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09592318.2021.1984709>
- Casiraghi, M. C., & Cusumano, E. (2023). Is someone’s mercenary another’s contractor? American, British, and Russian private security companies in US and UK parliamentary debates. *International Relations*, 00471178231159587. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00471178231159587>

Beyani, C. & Lilly, D. (2001) *Regulating private military companies: options for the UK Government*. International Alert, London, UK. ISBN 1898702073 <https://www.international-alert.org/publications/regulating-private-military-companies-options-for-the-uk-government/>

Nabiev, B. (2021). Ideological Factors Of Eliminating Threats To National Spirituality. Теория и практика современной науки, (12 (78)), 26-29. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/ideological-factors-of-eliminating-threats-to-national-spirituality>